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NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER
ANNUAL REPORT 2011 : APPENDICES

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Appendix A

Disciplines of Supported Projects 12/1/10- 8/31/11. Disciplines are reported by the Principle Investigator of the project. Projects may occur in more than one category.

Appendix B

Demographics of PI's and Co-PI's in Year 7

Appx B1: Gender of Project PI's and Co-PI's from 12/1/10–8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	GRADUATE FELLOW	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Female	9	2	1	2	8	4	17	43
Male	19	8	4	3	12	5	31	82
Do not wish to provide	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
TOTAL	28	13	5	5	20	9	48	128

Appx B2: Ethnicity of Project PI's and Co-PI's from 12/1/10–8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	GRADUATE FELLOW	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Hispanic or Latino	2	0	0	1	3	0	3	9
Not Hispanic or Latino	24	10	5	4	17	9	40	109
Do not wish to provide	2	3	0	0	0	0	5	10
TOTAL	28	13	5	5	20	9	48	128

Appx B3 Race of Project PI's and Co-PI's from 12/1/10–8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	GRADUATE FELLOW	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Asian	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	5
Black/African American	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Do not wish to provide	2	5	0	0	1	0	6	14
Hispanic/Latino	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Native Hawaiian/ Other Pacific Islander	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
White	24	8	5	3	16	8	39	103
TOTAL	27	13	5	4	18	9	46	122

Appx B4 Nationality of Project PI's and Co-PI's from 12/1/10–8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	GRADUATE FELLOW	LONG-TERM SABBATICAL	POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW	SHORT-TERM VISITOR	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
US Citizen	19	8	5	2	13	7	38	92
Permanent Resident	2	0	0	1	1	2	3	9
Non-US Citizen	7	2	0	2	6	0	7	24
Do not wish to provide	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
TOTAL	28	13	5	5	20	9	48	128

Appendix C

Demographics of Participants in NESCent Activities in Year 7

Appx C1: Gender of unique participants, irrespective of the number of visits to the center, in NESCent supported projects from 12/1/10–8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Do not wish to provide	0	2	0	2
Female	57	9	83	149
Male	128	18	144	290
(blank)	9	1	15	25
TOTAL	194	30	242	466

Appx C2: Ethnicity of unique participants, irrespective of the number of visits to the center, in NESCent supported projects from 12/1/10–8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Do not wish to provide	17	4	13	94
Hispanic or Latino	10	9	11	30
Not Hispanic or Latino	159	16	202	377
(blank)	8	1	16	25
TOTAL	194	30	242	466

Appx C3: Race of unique participants, irrespective of the number of visits to the center, in NESCent supported projects from 12/1/10–8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Asian	9	3	7	19
Black or African American	1	1	3	5
Do not wish to provide	16	6	13	35
Hispanic or Latino	4	5	6	15
Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	0	1	1	2
White	156	13	196	365
(blank)	8	1	16	25
TOTAL	194	30	242	466

Appx C4: Nationality of unique participants, irrespective of the number of visits to the center, in NESCent supported projects from 12/1/10–8/31/11

CATEGORY	CATALYSIS MEETING	COURSE	WORKING GROUP	GRAND TOTAL
Do not wish to provide	0	3	2	5
Non-US Citizen	67	13	51	131
Permanent Resident	12	2	9	23
US Citizen	107	11	164	282
(blank)	8	1	16	25
TOTAL	194	30	242	466

Appendix D

Countries based on home institution) of unique participants, irrespective of the number of visits to the center, in NESCent supported projects from 12/1/10-8/31/11

ARGENTINA	3	ISRAEL	1
AUSTRALIA	17	ITALY	1
AUSTRIA	2	JAPAN	3
BRAZIL	2	MEXICO	2
BULGARIA	1	NETHERLANDS	4
CANADA	29	NEW ZEALAND	4
CHINA	1	NORWAY	1
CROATIA	1	ROMANIA	1
DENMARK	1	SOUTH AFRICA	1
FINLAND	2	SPAIN	1
FRANCE	5	SWEDEN	4
GERMANY	17	SWITZERLAND	7
HUNGARY	1	UNITED KINGDOM	55
INDIA	2	UNITED STATES	541
IRELAND	1	GRAND TOTAL	711

PARTICIPANTS BY COUNTRY

Appendix E

States based on home institution) of unique participants, irrespective of the number of visits to the center, in NESCent supported projects from 12/1/10-8/31/11

ARMED FORCES	3	INDIANA	14	NEW YORK	24
ALASKA	2	KANSAS	6	OHIO	9
ALABAMA	3	KENTUCKY	3	OKLAHOMA	2
ARKANSAS	3	LOUISIANA	3	OREGON	11
ARIZONA	12	MASSACHUSETTS	20	PENNSYLVANIA	12
CALIFORNIA	74	MARYLAND	10	RHODE ISLAND	9
COLORADO	12	MAINE	1	SOUTH CAROLINA	4
CONNECTICUT	20	MICHIGAN	12	SOUTH DAKOTA	3
DC	7	MINNESOTA	5	TENNESSEE	15
DELAWARE	1	MISSOURI	6	TEXAS	12
FLORIDA	16	MONTANA	1	UTAH	1
GEORGIA	14	NORTH CAROLINA	120	VIRGINIA	12
HAWAII	4	NEBRASKA	6	WASHINGTON	9
IOWA	1	NEW HAMPSHIRE	4	WISCONSIN	7
IDAHO	3	NEW JERSEY	7	WYOMING	3
ILLINOIS	11	NEW MEXICO	4	TOTAL	541

PARTICIPANTS BY STATE

Appendix F: Detailed List of Activities and Participants in Year 7

CATALYSIS MEETINGS

High-throughput biodiversity research using eukaryotic metagenetics

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=264

Dates: 1/24/2011 - 1/27/2011

PI

Holly Bik

CoPI

W. Kelley Thomas

PARTICIPANTS

Shawn Polson
Anthony Chariton
Simon Creer
Jan Pawlowski
Mitchell Sogin
Franck Lejzerowicz
W. Kelley Thomas
Dorota Porazinska
Holly Bik
Simon Berger
Robin Giblin
Eric Allen
Tony Walters
Way Sung
Alexandros Stamatakis
Yijun Sun
Samantha Lewis
Greg Caporaso
Erik Pilgrim
Axayacatl Rocha-Olivares
Mark Blaxter
Mike Pfrender
Erick Matsen
Christopher Quince
Florent Angly

INSTITUTION

University of New Hampshire

INSTITUTION

University of New Hampshire

INSTITUTION

University of Delaware / NECC
CSIRO, Australia
Bangor University
University of Geneva
Marine Biological Lab, Woods Hole
University of Geneva
University of New Hampshire
University of Florida
University of New Hampshire
Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies (HITS gGmbH)
Davis University of Florida
Scripps Institution of Oceanography, UC San Diego
University of Colorado
University of New Hampshire
Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies (HITS gGmbH)
University of Florida
University of California, Riverside
University of Colorado
Environmental Protection Agency, Cincinnati
Centro de Investigación Científica y de Educación Superior de Ensenada (CICESE)
University of Edinburgh
University of Notre Dame
Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center
University of Glasgow
The University of Queensland, Australia

Evolution of infectious diseases: integrating empirical and modelling approaches

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=224

Dates: 3/22/2011 - 3/25/2011

PI

Sarah Reece

CoPI

Nicole Mideo
Andrew Read
Nick Savill

PARTICIPANTS

Aaron King
Mike Boots
Andreas Handel
Mark Wacker
Jessica Metcalf

INSTITUTION

Institutes of Evolution, Immunology and Infection Research

INSTITUTION

University of Edinburgh
Pennsylvania State University
University of Edinburgh

INSTITUTION

University of Michigan
University of Sheffield, UK
University of Georgia
Notre Dame
Princeton University, Oxford University

Adrian Smith	University of Oxford
Dan Haydon	University of Glasgow, UK
Nicole Mideo	University of Edinburgh
Amy Pedersen	University of Edinburgh, UK
Dave Barry	University of Glasgow, UK
Keith Matthews	University of Edinburgh, UK
Andrea Graham	Princeton
Deborah Cromer	University of New South Wales
Ruston Antia	Emory
Yael Artzy	University of Michigan
Nick Savill	University of Edinburgh
Michael Gilchrist	University of Tennessee
Andy Fenton	University of Liverpool
Bill Nelson	Queen's University, Canada
Beth Kochin	Emory University
Petra Schneider	University of Edinburgh, UK
Andrew Yates	Albert Einstein College of Medicine, US
Silvie Huijben	Penn State University
Ricardo Ramiro	University of Edinburgh, UK
Erida Gjini	University of Glasgow
Troy Day	Queen's University, Canada
Kathy Hanley	New Mexico State University
Andrew Read	Penn State University
James Lloyd-Smith	UCLA
Mike Ferdig	Notre Dame
Sarah Reece	Institutes of Evolution, Immunology and Infection Research
Daniel Coombs	University of British Columbia, Canada

Domestication as an evolutionary phenomenon: expanding the synthesis

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=218

Dates: 4/8/2011 - 4/11/2011

PI

Greger Larson

INSTITUTION

Durham University

CoPI

Michael Purugganan
Robin Allaby
Dolores Piperno
Dorian Fuller

INSTITUTION

New York University
University of Warwick
National Museum of Natural History
University College-London

PARTICIPANTS

Leilani Lucas
Paul Gepts
Rafael F Rubio de Casas
Tom Gilbert
Dorian Fuller
Tim Denham Monash
Robin Allaby
Leif Andersson
Keith Dobney
Kristen Gremillion
Fiona Marshall
Cynthia Climer
Lewis Lukens
Loukas Barton
Chris Pires
Kenneth Olsen
Andrew Doust
Manuel Arroyo-Kalin

INSTITUTION

University College-London
University of California, Davis
NESCent
University of Copenhagen
University College-London
University
University of Warwick
Uppsala University
Aberdeen University, UK
Ohio State University
Washington University St. Louis
Clemson University
University of Guelph
University of Alaska, Fairbanks
University of Missouri
Washington University in St. Louis
Oklahoma State University
Durham University

Peter J Richerson
Oris Sanjur Smithsonian
Dolores Piperno
Mary Jane West-Eberhard
Michael Purugganan
Greger Larson
Mark Thomas

University of California Davis
Tropical Research Institute
National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Tropical Research
Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
New York University
Durham University
UCL

Earth surface processes in the evolution of mammalian tooth shape

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=262

Dates: 4/27/2011 - 4/29/2011

PI

Richard Madden

CoPI

Matthew Kohn
Caroline A E Stromberg

PARTICIPANTS

Richard Madden
Daniel Flath
Caroline A E Stromberg
Laura Wilson
Matthew Kohn
Edgardo Latrubesse
Paul Baker
Sarah Feakins
Regan Dunn
Nicolas Cassar
Brittany Brand
Marcus Clauss
Rebecca Cuddahee
Alexandra van der Geer
Wendy Kuhne
Marith Reheis
Susan Williams
Peter Ungar
Philip Rundel
Rene Bobe
Mikael Fortelius
John Parkes
Samantha Evans
Alejandro Kramarz
Basil Gomez
Richard Kay
Christine M Janis
Jenny L McGuire
Siobhan Cooke
Nelson Beyer
Lauren Gonzales
Maxx Toler
Alejo Scarano
Steve Churchill

INSTITUTION

Duke University School of Medicine

INSTITUTION

Boise State University
University of Washington

INSTITUTION

Duke University School of Medicine
Macalester College
University of Washington
Kyoto University Museum
Boise State University
University of Texas-Austin
Duke University
University of Southern California
University of Washington
Duke University
University of Washington
University of Zurich (Switzerland)
Duke University
NCB Naturalis
Savannah River National Laboratory
USGS
Ohio University
University of Arkansas
University of California-Los Angeles
University of Georgia
University of Helsinki
Landcare Research
Boise State University
Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales
University of Hawaii
Duke University
Brown University
NESCent
Duke University
USGS
Duke University
Duke University
Universidad Nacional de La Plata
Duke University

Evolutionary Origins and Development of Woody Plants

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=287

Dates: 10/14/2011 - 10/17/2011

PI

Andrew Groover

CoPI

Quentin Cronk

PARTICIPANTS

Anjali Iyer-Pascuzzi

Quentin Cronk

William (Ned) Freidman

Matias Kirst

Valdimir Filkov

Aaron Liston

Pat Gensel

Neelima Sinha

Brook Moyers

William Stein

Malorie Taylor

Andrew Eckert

Rachel Spicer

Frederic Lens

David Neale

David Hearn

Andrew Groover

Ron Sederoff

Yka Helariutta

Rob Martienssen

Ove Nilsson

Carl Douglas

Matthew W Vaughn

INSTITUTION

US Forest Service and University of California-Davis

INSTITUTION

Department of Botany, University of British Columbia

INSTITUTION

Duke University

Department of Botany, University of British Columbia

Harvard University

University of Florida

University of California-Davis

Oregon State University

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

University of California-Davis

University of British Columbia

Binghamton University

University of California-Davis

Virginia Commonwealth University

Connecticut College

Netherlands Centre for Biodiversity Naturalis

University of California-Davis

Towson University

US Forest Service and University of California-Davis

North Carolina State Univeristy

University of Helsinki

Cold Spring Harbor Labs

Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

University of British Columbia

University of Texas-Austin

Modeling protein structural and energetic constraints on sequence evolution

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=288

Dates: 10/18/2011 - 10/21/2011

PI

David Liberles

CoPI

Sarah Teichmann

PARTICIPANTS

Ivet Bahar

Tina Perica

Richard Goldstein

Arne Elofsson

Mark Holder

Charles Brooks

Ugo Bastolla

Nikolay Dokholyan

Erich Bornberg-Bauer

Gina Cannarozzi

Joe Thornton

Sarah Teichmann

Ashley Teufel

Dan Weinreich

INSTITUTION

University of Wyoming

INSTITUTION

Cambridge University

INSTITUTION

University of Pittsburgh

Cambridge University

NIMR

Stockholm University

University of Kansas

University of Michigan

Spain

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

University of Muenster

University of Bern

HHMI/University of Oregon

Medical Research Council

University of Wyoming

Brown University

Gavin Naylor	College of Charleston
Simon Whelan	University of Manchester
David Liberles	University of Wyoming
Tal Pupko	Tel-Aviv University
Kimmen Sjolander	University of California-Berkeley
Jesse Bloom	Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center
Jeff Thorne	North Carolina State University
Johan Grahnén	University of Wyoming
David Swofford	Duke University
Shamil Sunyaev	Harvard Medical School
Eugene Shakhnovich	Harvard University
A.P. Jason de Koning	University of Colorado Denver, School of Medicine
David Pollock	University of Colorado-Denver
Nicholas Lartillot	University of Montreal
Lynne Regan	Yale University
Clemens Lakner	North Carolina State University
Simon Lovell	University of Manchester
Julian Echave	Universidad Nacional de San Martín
Dietlind Gerloff	University of California-Santa Cruz
Lucy Colwell	Cambridge University

The origin and evolution of animal-microbe interactions

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=263

Dates: 10/24/2011 - 10/27/2011

PI

Margaret McFall-Ngai

INSTITUTION

University of Wisconsin-Madison

CoPI

Michael G. Hadfield

INSTITUTION

University of Hawaii-Hilo

PARTICIPANTS

Gerard Eberl
 Jessica L Metcalf
 Andrew Knoll
 Margaret McFall-Ngai
 Nicole Dubilier
 Scott Gilbert
 Thomas Bosch
 Ann Reid
 Jan Sapp
 Michael G. Hadfield
 Jennifer Wernegreen
 Tadashi Fukami
 Diethard Tautz
 Hannah Carey
 Bernie Degnan
 Edward Ruby
 Sarkis Mazmanian
 Mary Rumpho
 Naomi Pierce
 Angela Douglas
 Natacha Kremer
 Jon Sanders
 Ute Hentschel
 Tomislav Domazet-Lošo
 Nicole King
 John Rawls
 Staffan Kjelleberg

INSTITUTION

Pasteur Institute
 University of Colorado-Boulder
 Harvard University
 University of Wisconsin-Madison
 Max Planck Institute
 Swarthmore College, University of Helsinki
 Christian-Albrechts University Kiel
 American Society of Microbiology
 York University
 University of Hawaii
 Duke University
 Stanford University
 Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Biology
 University of Wisconsin-Madison
 University of Queensland
 University of Wisconsin-Madison
 California Institute of Technology
 University of Maine
 Harvard University
 Cornell University
 University of Wisconsin-Madison
 Harvard University
 Julius-von-Sachs Institute for Biological Sciences
 Ruder Boskovic Institute
 University of California-Berkeley
 University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
 University of New South Wales

COURSES

Practical computing for biologists (and other scientists)

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=281

Dates: 6/6/2011 - 6/15/2011

PI

Steven Haddock

INSTITUTION

Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute

CoPI

Casey Dunn

INSTITUTION

Brown University

PARTICIPANTS

Casey Dunn

Steven Haddock

INSTITUTION

Brown University

Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute

Workshop on evolutionary quantitative genetics

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=275

Dates: 8/8/2011 - 8/13/2011

PI

Stevan J Arnold

INSTITUTION

Oregon State University (Corvallis,OR)

CoPI

Joe Felsenstein

INSTITUTION

TBD (NC STATES)

PARTICIPANTS

Debora Goedert

Josef Uyeda

Daniel Fulop

Vicente Diego Ortega Del Vecchyo

Cassia Oliveira

Marguerite Butler

Yakubu Abdulmojeed

Luke Harmon

Joe Felsenstein

Stevan J Arnold

Raul Sedano

Adam Jones

Maia Rafael

INSTITUTION

Ohio University

Oregon State University

University of California-Davis

University of California-Los Angeles

University of Nebraska-Lincoln

University of Hawaii

Cornell University

University of Idaho

University of Washington

Oregon State University

University of California-Los Angeles

Texas A & M University

University of Akron

Next-gen sequencing: data acquisition, comparative genomics, design and analysis for population genetics, systematics and development

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=282

Dates: 8/15/2011 - 8/29/2011

PI

Brian O'Connor

INSTITUTION

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

CoPI

Christine Elsik

James Noonan

William Cresko

Greg Wray

Jeffrey Townsend

Alexie Papanicolaou

Konrad Paszkiewicz

Jennifer Taylor

INSTITUTION

Georgetown University

Yale University

University of Oregon

Duke University

Yale University

CSIRO

University of Exeter

Australian National University

PARTICIPANTS

Kerin Bentley
 Suegene Noh
 Francesc Lopez
 Jeffrey Townsend
 Maria Jose Ruiz Lopez
 Jennifer Taylor
 Alexie Papanicolaou
 Julian Catchen
 Rajanikanth Govindarajulu
 Brian O'Connor
 Willam Cresko
 Iria Fernandez Silva
 MoÅLnica Munoz-Torres
 Konrad Paszkiewicz
 Alejandro Grajales

INSTITUTION

University of Georgia
 Kansas State University
 Giraldez Yale University
 Yale University
 University of Missouri
 Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation
 Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation
 University of Oregon
 University of Pittsburgh
 OICR
 University of Oregon
 University of Hawaii
 Georgetown University
 University of Exeter
 American Museum of Natural History

WORKING GROUPS

Costs of phenotypic plasticity and adaptation to novel environments

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=193

Dates: 12/8/2010 - 12/10/2010

PI

Courtney Murren

INSTITUTION

College of Charleston

CoPI

Carl Schlichting

INSTITUTION

University of Connecticut

PARTICIPANTS

Josh R Auld
 Mary Heskell
 Sarah Seiter
 Cameron Ghalambor
 Corey Handelsman
 Joel Kingsolver
 Ulrich Steiner
 Heidi Maclean
 David Pfennig
 Heather Maughan
 Courtney Murren
 Carl Schlichting
 Rick Relyea
 Joanna Masel
 Emilie Snell-Rood
 Hilary Callahan

INSTITUTION

NESCent
 Columbia University
 University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
 Colorado State University
 Colorado State University
 University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
 INSERM
 University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
 University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
 University of Toronto
 College of Charleston
 University of Connecticut
 University of Pittsburgh
 University of Arizona
 University of Indiana - Bloomington
 Barnard College

Grass phylogeny working group ii: inferring the complex history of c4 photosynthesis in grasses

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=202

Dates: 1/20/2011 - 1/21/2011

PI

Erika J Edwards

INSTITUTION

Brown University

CoPI

Nicolas Salamin
 Stephen Smith

INSTITUTION

University of Lausanne
 NESCent

PARTICIPANTS

Colin P Osborne
 J. Travis Columbus
 Erika J Edwards
 Khidir Hilu
 Stephen Smith
 Nicolas Salamin
 Pascal-Antoine Christin
 Melvin Duvall
 Elizabeth Kellogg
 Guillaume Besnard
 Beth Spriggs

INSTITUTION

University of Sheffield
 Rancho Santa Ana Botanic Garden
 Brown University
 Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
 Brown University
 University of Lausanne
 Brown University
 Northern Illinois University
 University of Missouri-St. Louis
 CNRS-University of Toulouse III
 Brown University

Evoci toolkit: concept inventories to assess conceptual understanding of evolution

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=258

Dates: 1/20/2011 - 1/23/2011

PI

Rebecca Price

CoPI

Kathryn Perez

PARTICIPANTS

Jory P Weintraub
 Tessa Andrews
 Gregory Davis
 Joel Abraham
 Louise S Mead
 Anna Thanukos
 Kathleen Fisher
 Bill McComas
 Mike Smith Mercer
 Sherry Southerland
 Kathryn Perez
 Mark Terry
 Rebecca Price

INSTITUTION

University of Washington-Bothell

INSTITUTION

University of Wisconsin at La Crosse

INSTITUTION

NESCent
 Montana State University
 Bryn Mawr College
 SimBiotic Software/Massachusetts Institute of Technology
 National Center for Science Education
 University of California, Museum of Paleontology
 San Diego State University, Semantic Research, Inc.
 University of Arkansas Main Campus (Fayetteville,AR)
 University School of Medicine
 Florida State University
 University of Wisconsin, La Crosse
 Northwest School
 University of Washington-Bothell

Determinants of extinction in ancient and modern seas

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=256

Dates: 1/27/2011 - 1/30/2011

PI

Paul G Harnik

CoPI

Rowan Lockwood
 Seth Finnegan

PARTICIPANTS

Rowan Lockwood
 Carl Simpson
 John Pandolfi
 Heike Lotze
 Zoe Finkel
 David Lindberg
 Paul G Harnik
 Sean Anderson
 Craig R McClain
 Aaron O'Dea
 Jenny L McGuire
 Seth Finnegan

INSTITUTION

Stanford University

INSTITUTION

College of William and Mary
 California Institute of Technology

INSTITUTION

College of William and Mary
 Museum für Naturkunde, Leibniz Institute at the Humboldt University
 University of Queensland, Australia
 Dalhousie University
 Mount Allison University
 University of California Berkeley
 Stanford University
 Dalhousie University
 NESCent
 Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
 NESCent
 California Institute of Technology

Synthesizing and databasing fossil calibrations: divergence dating and beyond

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=259

Dates: 3/3/2011 - 3/6/2011

PI

Daniel Ksepka

CoPI

James Parham

PARTICIPANTS

Rachel Warnock
Marcel van Tuinen
P. David Polly
JosA PatanA
Elizabeth Hermsen
Maria Gandolfo Nixon
Matthew Phillips
Walter Joyce
James Parham
Matthew Carrano
Mike Benton
Jason Head
Daniel Ksepka
Kristin Lamm
Jessica Ware

INSTITUTION

North Carolina State University

INSTITUTION

Alabama Museum of Natural History, University of Alabama,

INSTITUTION

University of Bristol
University of North Carolina-Wilmington
Indiana University
Instituto Butantan
Cornell University
Cornell University
University of Queensland
University of Tübingen
University of Alabama
Smithsonian Institution
University of Bristol
University of Toronto
North Carolina State University
North Carolina State University
Rutgers University-Newark

Tempo and mode of plant trait evolution: synthesizing data from extant and extinct taxa

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=269

Dates: 2/28/2011 - 3/4/2011

PI

William Cornwell

CoPI

Amy Zanne
Stephen Smith

PARTICIPANTS

Daniel McGlinn
Rafael F Rubio de Casas
Elisabeth Wheeler
Erika J Edwards
Jeremy Beaulieu
Brian O'Meara
William Cornwell
Stephen Smith
Risa Sargent
Rich FitzJohn
Mark Westoby
Amy Zanne
Ginger Jui
Dana Royer
Michael Donoghue
Richard Ree

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Brown University

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NESCent
North Carolina State University
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University of Tennessee, Knoxville
Vrije Universiteit
Brown University
University of Ottawa
University of British Columbia
Macquarie University
University of Missouri, St Louis
University of California, Berkeley
Wesleyan University
Yale University
The Field Museum

Modeling the diversification of human languages

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=255

Dates: 3/16/2011 - 3/19/2011

PI

Michael Gavin

PARTICIPANTS

Joe McCarter
Kathryn Kirby
Michael Gavin
Rob Dunn
Thiago Rangel
Rick Stepp
Claire Bower
Gregor Yanega
Michael Dunn
Russell Gray
Robert Colwell
Carlos A. Botero
Jennifer Verdolin

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Victoria University of Wellington

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University of British Columbia
Victoria University of Wellington
North Carolina State University
Universidade Federal de Goias
University of Florida
Yale University
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Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics
University of Auckland
University of Connecticut
NESCent
NESCent

Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=192

Dates: 3/21/2011 - 3/24/2011

PI

Margaret Hall

CoPI

Christopher Heesy
Andrew Iwaniuk

PARTICIPANTS

Shaun P. Collin
Christopher Heesy
Nathaniel Dominy
Bret Moore
Jeremy Corfield
Esteban Fernandez-Juricic
Thomas Lisney
Ellis Loew
Olaf RP Bininda-Emonds
Kara Yopak
Sonke Johnsen
Jason Kamilar
Gillian Moritz
Saul Nava
Margaret Hall

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Midwestern University

INSTITUTION

Midwestern University
Canadian Centre for Behavioural Neuroscience

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Midwestern University
Dartmouth College
Purdue University
University of Lethbridge
Purdue University
University of Alberta
Cornell University
Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg
University of California-San Diego
Duke University
Yale University
University of California-Santa Cruz
Harvard University
Midwestern University

Germination, trait coevolution, and niche limits in changing environments

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=201

Dates: 3/28/2011 - 3/30/2011

PI

Kathleen Donohue

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Duke University

CoPI

Rafael F Rubio de Casas

INSTITUTION

Duke University

PARTICIPANTS

Susan Kalisz
Kent Bradford
Jerry Baskin
Carol Baskin
Josh R Auld
Rafael Rubio de Casas
Lawrence Venable
James S. Clark
Johanna Schmitt
Liana Burghardt
Amity Wilczek
Charlie Willis
Jessica Metcalf
Susan Meyer
Jeannine Cavender-Bares
Kathleen Donohue

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University of California-Davis
University of Kentucky
University of Kentucky
NESCent
NESCent
University of Arizona
Duke University
Brown University
Duke University
Deep Springs College
Duke University
Oxford University
USDA Forest Service
University of Minnesota
Duke University

Integrative models of vertebrate sociality: evolution, mechanism and emergent properties

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=257

Dates: 4/1/2011 - 4/4/2011

PI

Dustin Rubenstein

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Columbia University

CoPI

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Steven Phelps
Eileen Lacey

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University of California, Berkeley

PARTICIPANTS

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Nancy Solomon
Iain Couzin
Michael Taborsky
Daniel Blumstein
Annaliese Beery
Jim Goodson
Ryan Earley
Hans Hofmann
EmA-lia Martins
Eileen Lacey
Loren Hayes
Peter Hurd
Dustin Rubenstein

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University of Bern
University of California-Los Angeles
Smith College
Indiana University
University of Alabama
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Indiana University
University of California-Berkeley
University of Louisiana-Monroe
University of Alberta
Columbia University

Origins of c4 grasslands: a new synthesis of phylogeny, ecology and paleobiology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=260

Dates: 4/7/2011 - 4/10/2011

PI

Colin P Osborne

CoPI

Christopher Still

Caroline A E Stromberg

PARTICIPANTS

Beth Forrestel

Benjamin H Passey

David Beerling

David Fox

Christopher Still

Michael Anderson

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William Hoffmann

Melinda Smith

Erika J Edwards

Nicolas Salamin

William Bond

Colin P Osborne

Caroline A E Stromberg

INSTITUTION

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University of Washington

INSTITUTION

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Johns Hopkins University

University of Sheffield

University of Minnesota

University of California-Santa Barbara

Wake Forest University

NCEAS

Macquarie University

North Carolina State University

Yale University

Brown University

University of Lausanne

University of Cape Town

University of Sheffield

University of Washington

Evolution and development of polyphenisms: pathways to innovation and diversification

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=149

Dates: 5/2/2011 - 5/4/2011

PI

David Pfennig

CoPI

Armin Moczek

PARTICIPANTS

Ian Dworkin

Sonia E Sultan

Emilie Snell-Rood

Matthew Wund

Tami Cruickshank

Cris C Ledon-Rettig

Carl Schlichting

Susan Foster

Fred Nijhout

Armin Moczek

David Pfennig

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University of Minnesota

The College of New Jersey

Indiana University

University of South Florida

University of Connecticut

Clark University

Duke University

University of Indiana

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Costs of phenotypic plasticity and adaptation to novel environments

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=193

Dates: 5/4/2011 - 5/6/2011

PI

Courtney Murren

CoPI

Carl Schlichting

PARTICIPANTS

Emilie Snell-Rood
David Pfennig
Rick Relyea
Mary Heskell
Ulrich Steiner
Sarah Seiter
Heather Maughan
Joanna Masel
Corey Handelsman
Cameron Ghalambor
Hilary Callahan
Joel Kingsolver
Josh R Auld
Courtney Murren
Carl Schlichting

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INSTITUTION

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University of Pittsburgh
Columbia University
Stanford University
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
University of Toronto
University of Arizona
Colorado State University
Colorado State University
Barnard College
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
NESCent
College of Charleston
University of Connecticut

Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=219

Dates: 5/5/2011 - 5/7/2011

CoPI

John Gowdy
David Wilson

PARTICIPANTS

Bernard Winograd
Nancy Martin
Dennis Embry
Peter Turchin
Harvey Whitehouse
David Rand
Kevin Kniffin
John Gowdy
Michael Cox
Greg DeAngelo
Tony Biglan
John Allman
John Barkley Rosser
David Wilson

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Evolution Institute
PAXIS Institute
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University of Oxford
Harvard University
Cornell University
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
Indiana University
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
Oregon Research Institute
California Institute of Technology
James Madison University
Binghamton University

Evolutionary mismatch and what to do about it

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=261

Dates: 5/2/2011 - 5/4/2011

PI

David Wilson

PARTICIPANTS

Nancy Martin
Bernard Winograd
Jerry Lieberman
David Harris
Jennifer Verdolin
Clinton D Francis
Martin Schlaepfer
Peter Turchin
Harvey Whitehouse
David Stephens
Joseph L Graves Jr
Elliott Sober
Lesley Newson
Andrew Sih
Terry Burnham
Elisabeth Lloyd
Marco Del Giudice
David Wilson

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Humanists of Florida Association
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NESCent
NESCent
INRA
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University of Minnesota
North Carolina A&T State University
University of Wisconsin
University of California
University of California
Harvard University
Indiana University
University of Turin
Binghamton University

Communicating the relevance of human evolution

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=203

Dates: 5/20/2011 - 5/22/2011

PI

Norman Johnson

CoPI

Louise S Mead
James J Smith

PARTICIPANTS

Sandra Ackerman
T. Ryan Gregory
Brad Williamson
Chelsea Crawford
Kristin Jenkins
Briana Pobiner
John M Logsdon
James J Smith
Caitlin Schrein
Rebecca Jordan
Jory P Weintraub
Robin A Smith
Craig Nelson
Randolph Nesse
Lauri Lebo Journalist
Louise S Mead
Norman Johnson

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University of Kansas
Fremont Union High School District
NESCent
Smithsonian Institution
University of Iowa
Michigan State University
Arizona State University
Rutgers University
NESCent
NESCent
Indiana University
University of Michigan
(Pennsylvania)
National Center for Science Education
University of Massachusetts-Amherst

Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=192

Dates: 6/27/2011 - 7/1/2011

PI

Margaret Hall

CoPI

Andrew Iwaniuk

Christopher Heesy

PARTICIPANTS

Gillian Moritz

Jason Kamilar

Andrew Iwaniuk

Saul Nava

Ellis Loew

Christopher Heesy

Bret Moore

Eric Warrant

Esteban Fernandez-Juricic

Olaf RP Bininda-Emonds

Sonke Johnsen

Kara Yopak

Shaun P. Collin

Margaret Hall

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Canadian Centre for Behavioural Neuroscience

Midwestern University

INSTITUTION

University of California

Yale University

University of Lethbridge

Harvard University

Cornell University

Midwestern University

Purdue University

University of Lund

Purdue University

Carl von Ossietzky Universitaet Oldenburg

Duke University

University of Western Australia

University of Western Australia

Midwestern University

Grass phylogeny working group ii: inferring the complex history of c4 photosynthesis in grasses

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=202

Dates: 6/28/2011 - 7/1/2011

PI

Erika J Edwards

CoPI

Nicolas Salamin

Stephen Smith

PARTICIPANTS

J. Travis Columbus

Pascal-Antoine

Khidir Hilu Virginia

Guillaume Besnard

Trevor Hodkinson

Beth Spriggs

Melvin Duvall

Erika J Edwards

Nicolas Salamin

Stephen Smith

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Christin Brown University

Polytechnic Institute and State University

CNRS-University of Toulouse III

Trinity College Dublin

Brown University

Northern Illinois University

Brown University

University of Lausanne

Brown University

University of Sheffield

Determinants of extinction in ancient and modern seas

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=256

Dates: 7/6/2011 - 7/9/2011

PI

Paul G Harnik

CoPI

Rowan Lockwood
Seth Finnegan

PARTICIPANTS

Heike Lotze
Derek Tittensor
John Pandolfi
David Lindberg
Jenny L McGuire
Carl Simpson
Craig R McClain
Zoe Finkel
Sean Anderson
Paul G Harnik
Rowan Lockwood
Seth Finnegan

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INSTITUTION

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World Conservation Monitoring Centre
University of Queensland
University of California Berkeley
NESCent
Humboldt University Berlin
NESCent
Mount Allison University
Simon Fraser University
Stanford University
College of William and Mary
California Institute of Technology

Evoci toolkit: concept inventories to assess conceptual understanding of evolution

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=258

Dates: 7/6/2011 - 7/8/2011

PI

Rebecca Price

CoPI

Kathryn Perez

PARTICIPANTS

Anna Hiatt
Terri McElhinny
Ryan Walker
Gregory Davis
Mike Smith
Joel Abraham
Mark Terry
Kathryn Perez
Louise Mead
Tessa Andrews
Rebecca Price

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INSTITUTION

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Oklahoma State University
Michigan State University
University of Arkansas Main Campus (Fayetteville,AR)
Bryn Mawr College
Mercer University School of Medicine
California State University-Fullerton
Northwest School
University of Wisconsin La Crosse
BEACON Center for the Study of Evolution in Action
Montana State University
University of Washington-Bothell

Large-scale demographic, network and behavioral trait analyses of sociality

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=285

Dates: 7/14/2011 - 7/17/2011

PI

Jennifer Fewell

CoPI

James H Hunt
Dustin Rubenstein

INSTITUTION

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INSTITUTION

North Carolina State University
Columbia University

PARTICIPANTS

Judith Korb
 Mauricio Gonzalez-Forero
 Dustin Rubenstein
 Jennifer Verdolin
 Collin McCabe
 Jennifer Fewell
 Charles Nunn
 Raghavendra Gadagkar
 Carlos A. Botero
 Andy Russell
 Patrick Abbot
 James H Hunt

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 Univ. Tennessee
 Columbia University
 NESCent
 Harvard University
 Arizona State University
 Harvard University
 Indian Institute of Science
 NESCent
 University of Exeter
 Vanderbilt University
 NC State University

Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=150

Dates: 7/28/2011 - 7/29/2011

PI

Christine E Wall

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Duke University

CoPI

Susan Williams
 Rebecca Z German
 Chris Vinyard

INSTITUTION

Ohio University
 Johns Hopkins University
 Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of Medicine and Pharmacy

PARTICIPANTS

Vladimir Gapeyev
 Rebecca Z German
 Chris Vinyard
 Susan Williams
 Christine E Wall

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NESCent
 Johns Hopkins University
 Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of Medicine and Pharmacy
 Ohio University
 Duke University

Origins of c4 grasslands: a new synthesis of phylogeny, ecology and paleobiology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=260

Dates: 9/22/2011 - 9/25/2011

PI

Colin P Osborne

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University of Sheffield

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Caroline A E Stromberg
 Christopher Still

INSTITUTION

University of Washington
 University of California-Santa Barbara

PARTICIPANTS

Beth Forrestel
 Melinda Smith
 William Bond
 Stephanie Pau
 Caroline Lehmann
 Chris Still
 Caroline A E Stromberg
 David Beerling
 Christopher Still
 Nicolas Salamin
 William Hoffmann
 David Fox
 Michael Anderson
 Erika J Edwards
 Benjamin H Passey
 Colin P Osborne

INSTITUTION

Yale University
 Yale University
 University of Cape Town
 NCEAS
 Macquarie University
 University of California-Santa Barbara
 University of Washington
 University of Sheffield
 University of California-Santa Barbara
 University of Lausanne
 North Carolina State University
 University of Minnesota
 Wake Forest University
 Brown University
 Johns Hopkins University
 University of Sheffield

Integrative models of vertebrate sociality: evolution, mechanism and emergent properties

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=257

Dates: 9/30/2011 - 10/2/2011

PI

Dustin Rubenstein

CoPI

Nancy Solomon

Steven Phelps

Eileen Lacey

PARTICIPANTS

Larry Young

John Wingfield

Steve Phelps

Loren Hayes

Michael Taborsky

Ryan Earley

Hans Hofmann

Peter Hurd

Daniel Blumstein

EmA-lia Martins

Jim Goodson

Iain Couzin

Nancy Solomon

Eileen Lacey

Annaliese Beery

Dustin Rubenstein

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University of Texas, Arlington

University of California, Berkeley

INSTITUTION

Emory University

University of California-Davis

University of Texas-Austin

University of Louisiana-Monroe

University of Bern

University of Alabama

University of Texas-Austin

University of Alberta

University of California-Los Angeles

Indiana University

Indiana University

Princeton University

Miami University

University of California-Berkeley

Smith College

Columbia University

How does cognition evolve?

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=22

Dates: 10/13/2011 - 10/14/2011

PI

Charles Nunn

PARTICIPANTS

Charles Nunn

Brian Hare

Collin McCabe

Tara Stoinski

Ludwig Huber

Evan MacLean

Jingzhi Tan

Jeff Stevens

Kara Schropfer

Alex Rosati

Yanjie Su

Chris Krupenye

Al Kamil

Ikuma Adachi

Daniel Haun

Filippo Aureli

Victoria Wobber

Carel van Schaik

INSTITUTION

University of California-Berkeley

INSTITUTION

Harvard University

Duke University

Harvard University

Zoo Atlanta and Dian Fossey Gorilla Fund

Messerli Institute (University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna, Medical University Vienna)

Duke University

Duke University

University of Nebraska

Duke University

Duke University

Peking University

Duke University

University of Nebraska

Kyoto University

Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology

Liverpool John Moores University

Harvard University

University of Zurich

Germination, trait coevolution, and niche limits in changing environments

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=201

Dates: 10/21/2011 - 10/23/2011

PI

Kathleen Donohue

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Duke University

CoPI

Rafael F Rubio de Casas

INSTITUTION

Duke University

PARTICIPANTS

Amity Wilczek
Xavier Morin
Jessica Metcalf
Charlie Willis
Lawrence Venable
Rafael Rubio de Casas
Susan Meyer
Liana Burghardt
Susan Kalisz
Kathleen Donohue
James S. Clark
Jeannine Cavender-Bares
Kent Bradford
Jerry Baskin
Carol Baskin
Josh R Auld
Sharon Strauss
Johanna Schmitt

INSTITUTION

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European Institute of Innovation and Technology
Princeton University
Duke University
University of Arizona
NESCent
USDA Forest Service
Duke University
University of Pittsburgh
Duke University
Duke University
University of Minnesota
University of California-Davis
University of Kentucky
University of Kentucky
NESCent
University of California-Davis
Brown University

An integrative evolutionary approach to examine sexual selection as a mechanism of speciation

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=194

Dates: 11/10/2011 - 11/14/2011

PI

Rebecca Safran

INSTITUTION

University of Colorado

CoPI

Albert Uy

INSTITUTION

Syracuse University

PARTICIPANTS

Albert Uy
Rebecca Safran

INSTITUTION

Syracuse University
University of Colorado

Tempo and mode of plant trait evolution: synthesizing data from extant and extinct taxa

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=269

Dates: 11/10/2011 - 11/14/2011

PI

William Cornwell

INSTITUTION

UC Berkeley

CoPI

Amy Zanne
Stephen Smith

INSTITUTION

University of Missouri-St. Louis
Brown University

PARTICIPANTS

Amy Zanne
Stephen Smith

INSTITUTION

University of Missouri, St Louis
NESCent

Appendix G:

Publications From NESCent Supported Projects in Year 7

CATALYSIS MEETINGS

Daniel Hartline
Petra Lenz
Mark Martindale
David Colman
Elaine Seaver
Günter Wagner

Daniel K. Hartline 2011 The evolutionary origins of glia, *Glia*, volume 59, issue 9, pp. 1215-1236

Daniel Faith
Jack Sites

Daniel E. Ruzzante and Jorge Rabassa 2011 Palaeogeography and palaeoclimatology of Patagonia: effects on biodiversity, *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, volume 103, issue 2, pp. 221-228

Daniel Hartline
Günter Wagner
Petra Lenz
Elaine Seaver
Mark Martindale
David Colman

Caroline H. Wilson and Daniel K. Hartline 2011 The novel organization and development of copepod myelin. II. Non-glial origin *The Journal of Comparative Neurology*

Elaine Seaver
David Colman
Daniel Hartline
Günter Wagner
Mark Martindale
Petra Lenz

Caroline H. Wilson and Daniel K. Hartline 2011 The novel organization and development of copepod myelin. II. Non-glial origin *The Journal of Comparative Neurology*

COURSE

Konrad Paszkiewicz
Brian O'Connor
Jeffrey Townsend
Greg Wray
Willam Cresko
James Noonan
Christine Elsik
Jennifer Taylor
Alexie Papanicolaou

Staci D. Bilbo, Gregory A. Wray, Sarah E. Perkins and William Parker 2011 Reconstitution of the human biome as the most reasonable solution for epidemics of allergic and autoimmune diseases *Medical Hypotheses* doi:10.1016/j.mehy.2011.06.019

GRADUATE FELLOW

Nimrod D Rubinstein

Nimrod D. Rubinstein, Adi Doron-Faigenboim, Itay Mayrose, and Tal Pupko 2011 Evolutionary models accounting for layers of selection in protein coding genes and their impact on the inference of positive selection *Mol Biol Evol* doi:10.1093/molbev/msr162

Nimrod D Rubinstein

Nimrod D. Rubinstein, David Zeevi, Yaara Oren, Gil Segal, and Tal Pupko 2011 The Operonic Location of Auto-Transcriptional Repressors is Highly Conserved in Bacteria *Mol Biol Evol* doi:10.1093/molbev/msr163

LONG-TERM SABBATICAL

Michael S Rosenberg	Anderson, C.D., and M.S. Rosenberg. 2011. Variation in association with manmade habitat edges exhibited by the Timber Rattlesnake (<i>Crotalus horridus</i>) in St. Louis County, Missouri. <i>Journal of Herpetology</i> 45(1):50-55.
Douglas Eernisse	Daniel I. Speiser, Douglas J. Eernisse and Sanke Johnsen. 2011, A Chiton Uses Aragonite Lenses to Form Images, <i>Current Biology</i> , volume 21, issue 8, pp. 665-670
Armin Moczek	Armin P. Moczek. 2011, Evolutionary biology: The origins of novelty, <i>Nature</i> , volume 473, issue 7345, pp. 34-35
Tal Pupko	A. Barzel, E. Privman, M. Peeri, A. Naor, E. Shachar, D. Burstein, R. Lazary, U. Gophna, T. Pupko and M. Kupiec 2011 Native homing endonucleases can target conserved genes in humans and in animal models, <i>Nucleic Acids Research</i> , volume 39, issue 15, pp. 6646-6659
Dorothee Huchon	Dirk Erpenbeck, Jagen Schmitz, Gennady Churakov, Dorothea Huchon, Gert Warheide and Bernard M. Degnan 2011 First evidence of miniature transposable elements in sponges (Porifera) <i>Hydrobiologia</i> DOI: 10.1007/s10750-011-0775-4
Tal Pupko	Eyal Privman, Osnat Penn, and Tal Pupko 2011 Improving the performance of positive selection inference by filtering unreliable alignment regions <i>Mol Biol Evol</i> doi:10.1093/molbev/msr177
Tal Pupko	Pupko, Tal 2011 Evolution after gene duplication <i>Trends in Evolutionary Biology</i> 10.4081/eb.2011.e1
Weigang Qiu	Xianfa Xie, Wei-Gang Qiu, and Peter Lipke 2011 Accelerated and adaptive evolution of yeast sexual adhesins <i>Mol Biol Evol</i> doi:10.1093/molbev/msr145

POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW

Josh R Auld	Escobar, J.S., J.R. Auld, A.C. Correa, J.M. Alonso, Y.K. Bony, J.M. Koene, J.P. Pointier, P. Jarne & P. David. Patterns of mating system evolution in hermaphroditic animals: correlations among selfing rate, inbreeding depression, and the timing of reproduction. <i>Evolution</i> .
Josh R Auld	Auld, J.R. & A. Charmantier. 2011. Life history of breeding partners alters age-related changes of reproductive traits in a natural population of blue tits. <i>Oikos</i>
Brian L. Sidlauskas	Sidlauskas, B.L. et al. (2011) Dealing with allometry in linear and geometric morphometrics: a taxonomic case study in the <i>Leporinus cylindriformis</i> group (Characiformes: Anostomidae) with description of a new species from Suriname. <i>Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society</i> . 162:103-130
Clinton D Francis	Francis, C., C. Ortega, et al. 2011. Different behavioural responses to anthropogenic noise by two closely related passerine birds. <i>Biology Letters</i> . doi:10.1098/rsbl.2011.0359.
Brian L. Sidlauskas	Alex Dornburg, Brian Sidlauskas, Francesco Santini, Laurie Sorenson, Thomas J. Near and Michael E. Alfaro (2011) The Influence of an Innovative Locomotor Strategy on the Phenotypic Diversification of Triggerfish (Family: Balistidae), <i>Evolution</i> , volume 65, issue 7, pp. 1912-1926
Jenny L McGuire	Anthony D. Barnosky, Nicholas Matzke, Susumu Tomiya, Guinevere O. U. Wogan, Brian Swartz, Tiago B. Quental, Charles Marshall, Jenny L. McGuire, Emily L. Lindsey, Kaitlin C. Maguire, Ben Mersey and Elizabeth A. Ferrer. 2011, Has the Earth's sixth mass extinction already arrived?, <i>Nature</i> , volume 471, issue 7336, pp. 51-57

Julie A Meachen-Samuels	Van Valkenburgh, B., A. Curtis, J. X. Samuels, D. Bird, B. Fulkerson, J. Meachen-Samuels, and G. Slater. 2011. Aquatic adaptations in the nose of carnivorans: evidence from the turbinates. <i>Journal of Anatomy</i> 218: 298-310.
Clinton D Francis	Francis, C.D., C. P. Ortega, and J. Hansen. 2011. Importance of juniper to birds nesting in pinyon-juniper woodlands in northwest New Mexico. <i>Journal of Wildlife Management</i> 75:1574-1580
Clinton D Francis	Francis, C. D., J. Paritsis, C. P. Ortega, & A. Cruz. 2011. Landscape patterns of avian habitat use and nest success are affected by chronic gas well compressor noise. <i>Landscape Ecology</i> doi:10.1007/s10980-011-9609-z.
Juan C Santos	Dendrobates rufulus Gorzula, 1990 is a poorly known dendrobatid, described from two specimens from the Chimanta Massif in the Venezuelan Guayana. We redescribe it based on six additional specimens and allocate this species to the genus Anomaloglossus. We also provide data on natural history, such as ecology, habitat, and vocalization.
Carlos A. Botero	Lovette IJ, Arbogast BS, Curry RL, Zink RM, Botero CA, Sullivan JP, Talaba AL, Harris RB, Rubenstein DR, Ricklefs RE, and E Bermingham (2011). Phylogenetic Relationships of the Mockingbirds and Thrashers (Aves: Mimidae). <i>Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution</i> . In press
Gordon Burleigh	J. G. Burleigh, M. S. Bansal, O. Eulenstein, S. Hartmann, A. Wehe and T. J. Vision 2011 Genome-Scale Phylogenetics: Inferring the Plant Tree of Life from 18,896 Gene Trees, <i>Systematic Biology</i> , volume 60, issue 2, pp. 117-125
Trina E Roberts	Trina E. Roberts, Hayley C. Lanier, Eric J. Sargis and Link E. Olson. 2011, Molecular phylogeny of treeshrews (Mammalia: Scandentia) and the timescale of diversification in Southeast Asia, <i>Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution</i> , volume 60, issue 3, pp. 358-372
Josh R Auld	Juan S. Escobar, Josh R. Auld, Ana C. Correa, Juan M. Alonso, Yves K. Bony, Marie-Agnes Coutellec, Joris M. Koene, Jean-Pierre Pointier, Philippe Jarne and Patrice David 2011 Patterns of Mating-System Evolution in Hermaphroditic Animals: Correlations Among Selfing Rate, Inbreeding Depression, and the Timing of Reproduction, <i>Evolution</i> , volume 65, issue 5, pp. 1233-1253
Benjamin D Redelings	Law, S. H. W., B. D. Redelings and S. W. Kullman. In press. Comparative Genomics of Duplicate γ -Glutamyl Transferase Genes in Teleosts: Medaka (<i>Oryzias latipes</i>), Stickleback (<i>Gasterosteus aculeatus</i>), Green Spotted Pufferfish (<i>Tetraodon nigroviridis</i>), Fugu (<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>), and Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>). JEZ part B.
Benjamin D Redelings	Revell, L. J., D. L. Mahler, P. R. Peres-Neto, and B. D. Redelings. In press. A new method for identifying exceptional phenotypic diversification. <i>Evolution</i> .
Jennifer Verdolin	Verdolin, J.L. In Press. Genetic variation of populations. In: <i>Encyclopedia of Race and Racism</i> , 2nd Edition.
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Peter J Unmack	M. Adams, S.D. Wedderburn, P.J. Unmack, M.P. Hammer and J. B. Johnson 2011 Use of Congeneric Assessment to Reveal the Linked Genetic Histories of Two Threatened Fishes in the Murray-Darling Basin, Australia, <i>Conservation Biology</i> , volume 25, issue 4, pp. 767-776
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SHORT-TERM VISITOR

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Claire Williams Claire G. Williams and Patrick Aderkas. 2011. Marking live conifer pollen for long-distance dispersal experiments, *Oecologia*, volume 165, issue 1, pp. 255-260

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WORKING GROUP

Rebecca Safran Albert Uy	Speciation with gene flow is greatly facilitated when traits subject to divergent selection also contribute to non-random mating. Such traits have been called “magic traits”, which could be interpreted to imply that they are rare, special, or unrealistic. Here, we question this assumption by illustrating that magic traits can be produced by a variety of mechanisms, including ones in which reproductive isolation arises as an automatic by product of adaptive divergence. We also draw upon the theoretical literature to explore whether magic traits have a unique role in speciation or can be mimicked in their effects by physically linked trait complexes. We conclude that magic traits are more frequent than previously perceived, but further work is needed to clarify their importance.
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Karen B Strier Susan C Alberts	William F. Morris, Jeanne Altmann, Diane K. Brockman, Marina Cords, Linda M. Fedigan, Anne E. Pusey, Tara S. Stoinski, Anne M. Bronikowski, Susan C. Alberts and Karen B. Strier. 2011, Low Demographic Variability in Wild Primate Populations: Fitness Impacts of Variation, Covariation, and Serial Correlation in Vital Rates, <i>The American Naturalist</i> , volume 177, issue 1, pp. E14-E28
Samantha Forde Ivana Gudelj	Hal L. Smith. 2011, Bacterial competition in serial transfer culture, <i>Mathematical Biosciences</i> , volume 229, issue 2, pp. 149-159
Arlin Stoltzfus Rutger Vos	Rutger A Vos, Jason Caravas, Klaas Hartmann, Mark A Jensen and Chase Miller. 2011, BIO::Phylo-phyloinformatic analysis using perl, <i>BMC Bioinformatics</i> , volume 12, issue 1, pp. 63
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Rafael F Rubio de Casas Kathleen Donohue	Rafael R. de Casas, Pablo Vargas, Esther Pérez-Corona, Esteban Manrique, Carlos García-Verdugo and Luis Balaguer 2011 Sun and shade leaves of <i>Olea europaea</i> respond differently to plant size, light availability and genetic variation, <i>Functional Ecology</i> , volume 25, issue 4, pp. 802-812
Catherine Graham Ken Kozak Carsten Rahbek	Carlos Daniel Cadena, Kenneth H. Kozak, Juan Pablo Gomez, Juan Luis Parra, Christy M. McCain, Rauri C. K. Bowie, Ana C. Carnaval, Craig Moritz, Carsten Rahbek, Trina E. Roberts, Nathan J. Sanders, Christopher J. Schneider, Jeremy VanDerWal, Kelly R. Zamudio, and Catherine H. Graham 2011 Latitude, elevational climatic zonation and speciation in New World vertebrates Proc. R. Soc. B doi:10.1098/rspb.2011.0720

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Appendix H: Press Coverage of NESCent Science and Activities for Year 7

POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWS

JOSH AULD:

“Biological clock ticks slower for female birds who choose good mates” (*Eurekalert*)

“Biological clock ticks slower for female birds who choose good mates” (*Science 360*, National Science Foundation)

“Biological clock ticks slower for female birds who choose good mates” (*USA Today*)

“How male birds affect female fertility” (*MSNBC*)

CARLOS BOTERO:

“Climate for divorce” (*Science News*)

CLINTON FRANCIS:

“Songbirds tweak their tunes in different ways to cope with clamor” (*Eurekalert*)

“C’mon feel the noise: Related songbirds respond differently to noise pollution, possibly complicating conservation efforts” (*Science Magazine*)

“Songbirds tweak their tunes in different ways to cope with clamor” (*Science 360* news highlights from NSF)

“Songbirds adapt to noisy environments” (*US News and World Report*)

“When birds go to town” (*Science News*)

JENNY MCGUIRE:

“Climate changes, and there goes the neighborhood” (*ScienceNews*)

“Study offers warning about next potential mass extinction” (*USA Today*)

“Earth’s sixth mass extinction: is it almost here?” (*National Science Foundation*)

RAFAEL RUBIO DE CASAS:

“The future of a fog oasis” (*Scientific American*)

JUAN SANTOS:

“Treadmill tests for poison frogs prove toxic species are more physically fit” (*Eurekalert*)

“Poisonous lifestyle makes frogs more fit” (*Wired Science*)

“Treadmill test reveals most poisonous frogs are best frog athletes” (*Discovery Channel: Animal Planet*)

“Athletic frogs: Go bold or go home” (*Futurity*)

“Froggy fitness: toxic species prove most athletic” (*LiveScience*)

“Poison frog athletes” (*California Academy of Sciences*)

“Poison dart frogs leap to the top for frog fitness” (*MSNBC News*)

STEPHEN SMITH:

“Single parenthood doesn’t pay off for plants” (*Eurekalert*)

PETER UNMACK:

“Little Aussie Batter” (*Good Weekend Magazine*, Melbourne)

GREGOR YANEGA:

“Hummingbirds catch flying bugs with the help of fast-closing beaks” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2011-07/nesc-hcf071911.php

CATALYSIS MEETINGS AND WORKING GROUPS

**LAUREN BUCKLEY ET AL.: MECHANISTIC DISTRIBUTION MODELS:
ENERGETICS, FITNESS, AND POPULATION DYNAMICS**

“Coping with climate change” (*Eurekalert*)

ALEXEI DRUMMOND ET AL.: SOFTWARE FOR BAYESIAN EVOLUTIONARY ANALYSIS BY SAMPLING TREES:

“Ancestry of polar bears traced to Ireland” (*ScienceDaily*)

NORMAN JOHNSON ET AL.: COMMUNICATING THE RELEVANCE OF HUMAN EVOLUTION

“Panelists to discuss evolution of human brain size, skin color and diet at AAAS meeting” (*Eurekalert*)

“Thinking big” (*Science News*)

“Eating meat drove the evolution of our big, powerful brain” (*AAAS Meeting Coverage. National Association of Science Writers*)

“Human brain evolution and creatine gene expression” (*Scitable*)

“Just how big a deal is milk drinking?” (*Scientific American*)

**KEN KOZAK ET AL.: MONTANE DIVERSITY IN SPACE AND TIME:
LINKING EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY AND MACROECOLOGY**

“Stable temperatures boost biodiversity in tropical mountains” (*Eurekalert*)

**JONATHAN PAYNE ET AL.: PHANEROZOIC BODY SIZE TRENDS IN TIME AND SPACE:
MACROEVOLUTION AND MACROECOLOGY**

“Marine snails get a metabolism boost” (*Eurekalert*)

**KAREN STRIER AND SUSAN ALBERTS:
EVOLUTIONARY ECOLOGY OF PRIMATE LIFE HISTORIES**

“Primates are more resilient than other animals to environmental ups and downs” (*Eurekalert*)

“Planet of the apes...and monkeys and humans” (*TIME Magazine*)

“Primates better adapted to environmental changes” (*Birmingham Star*)

“Primates best at coping with change” (*St. Louis Globe-Democrat*)

“Lovely weather for ducks and primates” (*Futurity*)

“Aging rates, gender gap in mortality similar across all primates” (*Eurekalert*)

“Humans age at same rate as chimps, gorillas” (*Discovery News*)

“Humans age at same pace as other primates, study finds” (*US News & World Report*)

“Humans, apes, have similar aging patterns” (*ABC News*)

“What do you mean I’m aging like a baboon?!” (*MSNBC News*)

“Study finds primates age gracefully” (*National Science Foundation*)

“Science podcast” (*Science Magazine*)

“To age is primate” (*Duke News*)

“Humans, apes, have similar aging patterns” (*USA Today*)

“Nonhuman primates and humans have similar aging patterns, study shows” (*Los Angeles Times*)

“Despite long lives, humans age like other primates” (*NPR’s Science Friday*)

“Talk of the Nation: Despite long lives, humans age like other primates” (*NPR*)

“Humans, primates age in similar ways” (*CBS News*)

“Humans, apes, have similar aging patterns” (*Seattle Times*)

“Humans, monkeys age the same way” (*Futurity*)

“Time marches on for aging people in about the same way as for our primate cousins, study finds” (*News Radio Toronto*)

“When it comes to aging, we’re just like monkeys” (*The Globe and Mail*)

“Research insights: What it means to be human” (*The Examiner*)

VISITING SCHOLARS

RYAN CALSBEEK

“Of lizards, female choice and male competition” (*Science in the Triangle*)

TAL PUPKO

“New study pinpoints why some microbial genes are more promiscuous than others” (*EurekaAlert*)

EDUCATION AND OUTREACH GROUP

DARWIN DAY ROAD SHOW

“A nationwide day for honoring Charles Darwin, but handled with caution” (*New York Times*)

“It’s cool, really, we promise” (*GenomeWeb*)

“Evolution: Only in America” (*BioJobBlog*)

NESCENT EVOLUTION FILM FESTIVAL

“Cold-blooded cannibals: extreme adaptations to island life” (*UK Guardian*)

“Crafty island plants use lizards to disperse their seeds” (*UK Guardian*)

NESCENT LEADERSHIP AND STAFF

JOEL KINGSOLVER

“Evolution drives many plants and animals to be bigger, faster” (*EurekaAlert*)

CRAIG MCCLAIN

“The mass extinction of scientists who study species” (*Wired Magazine*)

“Scientists take Charles Darwin on the road” (*Miller-McCune*)

“Life under constant pressure” (*Miller-McCune*)

Appendix I: Active Projects in Year 7

(Project Titles Are Hyperlinks)

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
CATALYSIS MEETING				
Richard Moore Tia-Lynn Ashman	Miami University-Oxford University of Pittsburgh	Emergence of gender and sex chromosomes: evolutionary insights from a diversity of taxa	5/1/2010	4/30/2011
James H Hunt	North Carolina State University	Evolution of insect sociality: an integrative modeling approach	4/1/2010	3/31/2011
Greger Larson Dolores Piperno Robin Allaby Michael Purugganan Dorian Fuller	Durham University National Museum of Natural History University of Warwick New York University University of College-London	Domestication as an evolutionary phenomenon: expanding the synthesis	4/1/2010	3/31/2011
Sarah Reece Andrew Read Nick Savill Nicole Mideo	Institutes of Evolution, Immunology and Infection Research Pennsylvania State University University of Edinburgh University of Edinburgh	Evolution of infectious diseases: integrating empirical and modeling approaches	5/1/2010	4/30/2011
Richard Madden Matthew Kohn Caroline A E Stromberg	Duke University School of Med. Boise State University University of Washington	Earth surface processes in the evolution of mammalian tooth shape	10/10/2010	10/10/2011
Margaret McFall-Ngai Michael G. Hadfield	University of Wisconsin-Madison University of Hawaii-Hilo	The origin and evolution of animal-microbe interaction	10/10/2010	10/10/2011
Holly Bik W. Kelley Thomas	University of New Hampshire University of New Hampshire	High-throughput biodiversity research using eukaryotic metagenetics	10/10/2010	10/10/2011
Andrew Groover Quentin Cronk	US Forest Service and University of California-Davis Department of Botany, University of British Columbia	Evolutionary Origins and Development of Woody Plants	5/1/2011	4/30/2012
David Liberles Sarah Teichman	University of Wyoming Cambridge University	Modeling protein structural and energetic constraints on sequence evolution	5/1/2011	4/30/2012
Jason Wolf Francisco Ubeda Hamish Spencer	University of Bath University of Tennessee-Knoxville University of Otago (New Zealand)	An integrative understanding of the evolution of genomic imprinting	5/1/2011	4/30/2012
Eric Crandall Cynthia Riginos	University of California-Santa Cruz University of Queensland	The Molecular Ecology and Evolution of the Indo-Pacific: A Collaborative Research Network	5/1/2011	4/30/2012
COURSE				
Stevan J Arnold Joe Felsenstein	Oregon State University TBD (NC States)	Workshop on evolutionary quantitative genetics	8/8/2011	8/13/2011
Steven Haddock Casey Dunn	Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute Brown University	Practical computing for biologists (and other scientists)	6/6/2011	6/15/2011
Brian O'Connor Konrad Paszkiewicz Alexie Papanicolaou Jeffrey Townsend Greg Wray William Cresko James Noonanand Christine Elsik Jennifer Taylor	Univ. of North Carolina Chapel Hill University of Exeter CSIRO Yale University Duke University University of Oregon Yale University Georgetown University Australian National University	Next-gen sequencing: data acquisition, comparative genomics, design analysis for population genetics, systematics and development	8/15/2011	8/29/2011

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
GRADUATE FELLOW				
Bret Moore	Purdue University	Do retinal specializations reflect ecology? An evolutionary perspective	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Paul Durst	Duke University	Evaluating patterns and trends in insular body size evolution	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Sarah Seiter	Univ. of North Carolina Chapel Hill	Distinguishing trait value and trait plasticity in the evolution of reaction norms	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Nimrod D Rubinstein	Tel-Aviv University	Detection of clade-specific accelerations and decelerations in gene evolution rates	9/20/2010	12/10/2010
Luke Mahler	Harvard University	Improving and testing ecological models of phenotypic diversification	9/1/2010	12/10/2010
LONG-TERM SABBATICAL				
Armin Moczek	Indiana University-Bloomington	The nature of nurture: how environmental and genetic information interact to shape development and evolution	9/1/2010	6/3/2011
Dorothee Huchon	Tel-Aviv University	Current view of rodent phylogenetic relationships	9/1/2010	8/31/2011
Tal Pupko	Tel-Aviv University	Evolutionary models accounting for multi- layer selection pressures	9/1/2010	8/31/2011
Weigang Qiu	Hunter College, City University of New York	Bioinformatics: building a novel and effective career path to evolutionary biology	10/1/2010	6/30/2011
Dena Smith	University of Colorado	Evolution of the Coleoptera: A Paleontological Perspective	7/1/2011	1/1/2012
POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW				
Josh R Auld	NESCent	Evaluating the effects of inbreeding on dispersal	10/1/2009	7/30/2011
Carlos A Botero	NESCent	Evolution of conventional signals: from individuals to populations and back	1/1/2009	12/31/2011
Trina E Roberts	NESCent	Sticky tips and misplaced roots: is there a bias in intraspecific phylogenetics?	8/1/2008	7/31/2011
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	NESCent	Competition, guild structure and evolution in the carnivora	8/1/2009	7/31/2012
Benjamin D Redelings	NESCent	Improved probabilistic models of insertion/ deletion for phylogenetic inference	9/1/2009	8/31/2012
Liam J Revell	NESCent	Process and pattern in the phylogenetic analysis of comparative data	8/1/2009	1/15/2011
Juan C Santos	NESCent	Multivariate evolutionary analysis: integrating structural equation modeling and phylogenetics	10/1/2009	9/30/2012
Gregor Yanega	NESCent	A comparative phylogenetic approach to the study of insular avian phenotypes	8/1/2009	7/30/2011
Peter J Unmack	NESCent	A gis based approach to a priori prediction in aquatic biogeography	8/1/2010	7/31/2012
Jenny L McGuire	NESCent	Examining paleontological extinction patterns to predict modern extinction vulnerability	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent	Integrating behavioral syndromes into social networks: optimal distribution of phenotypes and group stability	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Clinton D Francis	NESCent	Acoustic signal space conservatism: a framework for signal flexibility in noise	1/1/2011	1/1/2013
Rafael F Rubio de Casas	NESCent	Dispersal evolution in the angiosperms: the origin of heterocarpy	5/1/2010	4/30/2012
Adam Smith	NESCent	Evaluating Effects of Temporal Distribution of Fossil Calibrations on Divergence Analyses	9/1/2011	9/1/2013

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW (continued)				
Paul G Hamik	NESCent	Ecological controls on evolutionary rates in marine systems	9/1/2011	9/1/2011
Kate Hertweck	NESCent	Comparative biology of transposable element proliferation	8/8/2011	8/8/2013
Mira Han	NESCent	Gene evolution in genomic context: Integrating genomic location into gene evolution models	9/1/2011	9/1/2013
Tami Cruickshank	NESCent	Population genetics of maternal effects and their influence on molecular evolution	10/1/2011	10/1/2013
SHORT-TERM VISITOR				
Matina Kalcounis-Ruppell	UNC Greensboro	Potential for peripheral populations to mitigate core extinctions: bats and white nose syndrome	10/1/2010	12/31/2010
Ryan Calsbeek	Dartmouth College	The adaptive landscape in evolutionary biology	11/1/2010	2/28/2011
Louise Comas	University of California-Davis	Character evolution in root systems of woody plants	1/31/2011	2/11/2011
Diddahally Govindaraju	Boston University	Signatures of multilevel selection in human health	4/4/2011	7/1/2011
Olav Rueppell	University of North Carolina-Greensboro	The influence of genetic architecture on the effect of sex and recombination on genotypic offspring diversity	1/25/2011	4/25/2011
Pam Soltis	University of Florida	Reconstructing the Great Tree of Life	9/1/2011	11/30/2011
Douglas Soltis	University of Florida	Reconstructing the Great Tree of Life	9/1/2011	11/30/2011
Rebecca Safran	University of Colorado	An integrative evolutionary approach to examine sexual selection as a mechanism of speciation	6/6/2011	6/10/2011
Carl Simpson	Museum fuer Naturkunde, Leibniz Institute at the Humboldt University Berlin	Understanding the role of coloniality and photosymbiosis in coral macroevolution	6/1/2011	9/1/2011
WORKING GROUP				
Alexei Drummond Marc Suchard Andrew Rambaut	University of Auckland University of California-LA University of Edinburgh	Software for bayesian evolutionary analysis by sampling trees	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Margaret Hall Andrew Iwaniuk Christopher Heesy	Midwestern University Canadian Centre for Behavioural Neuroscience Midwestern University	Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Courtney Murren Carl Schlichting	College of Charleston University of Connecticut	Costs of phenotypic plasticity and adaptation to novel environments	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Rebecca Safran Albert Uy	University of Colorado Syracuse University	An integrative evolutionary approach to examine sexual selection as a mechanism of speciation	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Kathleen Donohue Rafael F Rubio de Casas	Duke University Duke University	Germination, trait coevolution, and niche limits in changing environments	11/1/2009	10/31/2011
Erika J Edwards Stephen Smith Nicolas Salamin	Brown University NESCent University of Lausanne	Grass phylogeny working group ii: inferring the complex history of c4 photosynthesis in grasses	11/1/2009	10/31/2011
Norman Johnson James J Smith Louise S Mead	Univ. of Massachusetts-Amherst Michigan State University National Center for Science Edu.	Communicating the relevance of human evolution	11/1/2009	10/31/2011
David Wilson John Gowdy	Binghamton University Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute	Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics	5/1/2010	4/30/2012

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
WORKING GROUP (continued)				
Michael Gavin	Victoria University of Wellington	Modeling the diversification of human languages	10/10/2010	10/10/2012
Paul G Hamik Seth Finnegan Rowan Lockwood	Stanford University California Institute of Technology College of William and Mary	Determinants of extinction in ancient and modern seas	10/10/2010	10/10/2012
Dustin Rubenstein Steven Phelps Nancy Solomon Eileen Lacey	Columbia University University of Texas, Arlington Miami University University of California, Berkeley	Integrative models of vertebrate sociality: evolution, mechanism and emergent properties	10/10/2010	10/10/2012
Rebecca Price Kathryn Perez	University of Washington-Bothell University of Wisconsin at La Crosse	Evocci toolkit: concept inventories to assess conceptual understanding of evolution	10/10/2010	10/10/2012
Daniel Ksepka James Parham	North Carolina State University Alabama Museum of National History, University of Alabama	Synthesizing and databasing fossil calibrations: divergence dating and beyond	10/10/2010	10/10/2012
Colin P Osborne Caroline A E Stromberg Christopher Still	University of Sheffield University of Washington University of California-Santa Barbara	Origins of c4 grasslands: a new synthesis of phylogeny, ecology and paleobiology	10/10/2010	10/10/2012
David Wilson	Binghampton University	Evolutionary mismatch and what to do about it	10/10/2010	10/10/2012
William Cornwell Stephen Smith Amy Zane	UC Berkeley Brown University Univ. of Missouri-St. Louis	Tempo and mode of plant trait evolution: synthesizing data from extant and extinct taxa	12/1/2010	12/1/2012
Jennifer Fewell James H Hunt Dustin Rubenstein	Arizona State University North Carolina State University Columbia University	Large-scale demographic, network and behavioral trait analyses of sociality	5/1/2011	4/30/2013
Doris Bachtrog Judith Mank Catherine Peichel	University of CA-Berkeley University of Oxford Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center	The tree of sex—a comprehensive synthesis of sex determination systems in eukaryotes	5/1/2011	4/30/2013
Arlin Stoltzfus Rutger Vos Enrico Pontelli	Center for Advanced Research in Biotechnology University of Reading New Mexico State University	HIP: Hackathons, Interoperability, Phylogenies	5/1/2011	4/30/2013

Appendix J: Projects Supported in Year 7

(Project Titles Are Hyperlinks)

CATALYSIS MEETING

Sarah Teichmann David Liberles	Modeling protein structural and energetic constraints on sequence evolution
Quentin Cronk Andrew Groover	Evolutionary Origins and Development of Woody Plants
Hamish Spencer Francisco Ubeda Jason Wolf	An integrative understanding of the evolution of genomic imprinting
Cynthia Riginos Eric Crandall	The Molecular Ecology and Evolution of the Indo-Pacific: A Collaborative Research Network

JOURNALIST IN RESIDENCE

Molly Samuel	Shipwrecked on Dry Land: a documentary for public radio
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LONG-TERM SABBATICAL

Dena Smith	Evolution of the Coleoptera: A Paleontological Perspective
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POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW

Kate Hertweck	Comparative biology of transposable element proliferation
Adam Smith	Evaluating Effects of Temporal Distribution of Fossil Calibrations on Divergence
Mira Han	Gene evolution in genomic context: Integrating genomic location into gene evolution models
Tami Cruickshank	Population genetics of maternal effects and their influence on molecular evolution
Robert Lanfear	Synthesizing methods and data to understand the mutational processes that shape genomes
Paul G Hamik	Ecological controls on evolutionary rates in marine systems
Elizabeth J Sbrocco	Exploring environmental correlates of range limits across a marine biodiversity hotspot

SHORT-TERM VISITOR

Rebecca Safran	An Integrative Evolutionary Approach to Examine Sexual Selection as a Mechanism of Speciation
Pam Soltis	Reconstructing the Great Tree of Life
Douglas Soltis	Reconstructing the Great Tree of Life
Carl Simpson	Understanding the role of coloniality and photosymbiosis in coral macroevolution

WORKING GROUP

Catherine Peichel Judith Mank Doris Bachtrog	The tree of sex—a comprehensive synthesis of sex determination systems in eukaryotes
Dustin Rubenstein James H Hunt Jennifer Fewell	Large-scale demographic, network and behavioral trait analyses of sociality
Rutger Vos Enrico Pontelli Arlyn Stoltzfus	HIP: Hackathons, Interoperability, Phylogenies